

Resistance of rice varieties to WBPH at Banswara, India, 1986 wet season.

Variety	Cross	Damage rating ^a	Reaction ^b
RPW6-18	IR8/Siam 9	7	S
Pusa 44-33	IR5901-2/IR8	9	HS
R35-2750	IR8JW1263	4	MR
RP825-28-7-1	Vijaya/PTB21	6	S
RP25-45-1-3	Vijaya/PTB21	5	MR
BR51-46-1-0-1	IR20/IR5-114-3	7	S
IR52	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071//IR206	5	MR
RP1670-1418-2208-1585	M63-83/Cauvery	8	HS
RAU72-9-20-1-1	IR8/IR12-178	4	MR
UPR239-151-1-1	Hamsa/IR24	7	S
UPR231-28-1-2	Ratna/YR13-89-11	5	MR
RP1898-6	Mettasanna/Rasi	5	MR
HKR 101	—	5	MR
RP2151-40-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	3	R
RP2151-21-22	IET4141/CR98-7216	4	MR
RP1831-36-1-4	Surekha/CR147-7369	1	R
RP1832-23-3-4	CR141-7404/Surekha	2	R
RR5 1-1	ARC6650/TNI//Mudgo/PTB 33	8	HS
RP2086-74-6-1	IET5854/IET6187	9	HS
CR314-5-10	—	8	HS
CR314-5-3	—	9	HS
RP2240-86-84	RP143-4/Phalguna	3	R
RP2240-153-151	RP143-4/Phalguna	5	MR
RP2246-72	Pusa 2-21/Surekha	6	S
HKP20	—	4	MR
AR26-5-3-5	Paizam/IR8	2	R
NRL-162	Jaya mutant/Bas. 370	6	S
SKL-17-67-11	W13400/W11216	6	S
Pusa 587-2-1	—	2	R
RNDR88-1-1	IR36/T21	3	R
UPR79-151	—	6	S
UPRS1-47	—	6	S
KD3-5-13	—	4	MR
RP9263-2256-2	Sona/ARC1154	5	MR
RP2263-2561-1	Sona/ARC1154	7	S
RP1686-616-1	IET3262/Dhaneswar	9	HS
RP2440-32-28	RP143-4/Phalguna	7	S
RP2240-142-139	RP143-4/Phalguna	7	S
RR52-1	CR188-10/Indira	9	HS
IR18348-36-3-3	IR5657-33-2-1/IR2061-465-1-5-5	3	R
BK79	—	6	S
BK190	—	7	S
BK398	—	5	MR
BK657	—	8	HS
Chambal	—	4	MR
BK770	—	5	MR
CR220-66	—	6	S
Ratna	—	8	HS
Jaya	—	9	HS
IR36	—	6	S

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Eight varieties scored resistant and 15 moderately resistant (see table). Eleven were highly susceptible. RP1831-36-1-4, RP1832-23-3-4, AR26-5-3-5. and Pusa 587-2-1 showed high resistance; Jaya, Pusa 44-33, CR314-5-3, RP1686-616-1, RR52-1, and RP2086-74-6-1 were highly susceptible. □

Pothana — a gall midge (GM) resistant variety for endemic areas of Andhra Pradesh

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Pothana (IR579/ W12708), recently released for GM endemic areas, is 90 cm tall and produces compact, dense panicles and long slender grains. The leaf margin and other plant parts are purple. It matures in 125 d during the monsoon and 135 d during the winter seasons. It is almost immune to GM attack and is tolerant of yellow stem borer.

In trials from 1982 to 1984, Pothana yielded an average 4.3 t/ha. Because GM incidence is high in the monsoon crop, the yield advantage in this season is spectacular. Among 64 varieties tested at 21 locations in 1981, Pothana ranked second with a grain yield of 4 t/ha. □

Evaluation for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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We evaluated field resistance to BPH of 13 cultivars, including Jaya and Ratna

Field resistance of rice varieties to BPH in Cuttack, Orissa, India, 1983.

Variety	BPH no./hill at 90 DT	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t/ha)
OR131-13-13	11.4	86	4.9
IR13429-196-1-20	19.6	82	4.2
IR36	63.1	87	4.2
OR131-11	7.7	96	4.0
CR157-22-1900	32.9	91	4.0
IR1342-108-2-2-3	32.2	85	3.9
OR158-13-1	197.5	88	3.4
OR131-3-1	8.9	100	3.3
OR136-3	16.5	99	2.9
Ratna	217.6	82	2.6
Jaya	112.3	98	2.6
OR131-3-3	9.7	98	2.4
IR19661-364-1-2-3	9.4	96	2.0

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